

Strategy

Search term groups:

osteoblasts – osteoblast precursors – osteoclasts – osteoclast precursors – bone related words – co-culture related words

Search steps

Include studies mentioning osteoblasts OR osteoblast precursors in combination with bone related words
AND

Include studies mentioning osteoclasts OR osteoclast precursors in combination with bone related words
AND

include studies mentioning co-cultures

WEB OF SCIENCE

Osteoblast

TS=(Osteoblast* OR Pre-osteoblast* OR preosteoblast* OR osteoprogenitor* OR (“Bone forming” OR osteogenic) NEAR/3 cells)

Osteoblast progenitor

TS=(“Mesenchymal stem” OR “Mesenchymal stromal” OR “Mesenchymal progenitor” OR “bone marrow stem” OR “Bone marrow stromal” OR MSC* OR “Multipotent stem” OR “Multipotent stromal” OR “Multi-potent stem” OR “Multi-potent stromal” OR “Stromal cell” OR “Stromal fraction” OR “Adipose derived stem” OR “Adipose derived stromal” OR “Adipose stem” OR “Adipose stromal” OR “Fat derived stem” OR “Fat derived stromal” OR MC3T3* OR “Periodontal ligament” NEAR/3 cell* OR “MLO-Y4” OR “MLO Y4” OR “MLO A5” OR “MLO-A5”)

Bone related

TS=(Bone AND (development OR formation OR tissue OR remodel* OR re-model* OR forming OR model) OR skelet* OR bone* OR resorbing OR (Mineral* AND matrix AND deposit*) OR Resorpt* OR Osteopor* OR osteopetro* OR bone diseas* OR osteolysis OR ossification)

Osteoclast

TS=(osteoclast* OR pre-osteoclast* OR preosteoclast* OR “resorbing cells” OR odontoclast* OR cementoclast*)

osteoclast precursors

TS=(Macrophage NEAR/0 Precursor* OR macrophage-like NEAR/3 cell* OR monocy* OR monoblast* OR promonocy* OR THP* OR RAW264* OR RAW NEAR/0 264* OR RAW-264* OR Mononuclear NEAR/0 cell* OR “Mononuclear fraction” OR ((Hematopoietic OR haematopoietic) AND (stem OR stromal)))

Co-culture

TS=(co-cult* OR cocult* OR coincubat* OR co-incubat* OR multi-cultur* OR multicultur* OR tri-cultur* OR tricultur* OR “cultured together” OR “cultivated together” OR Cell NEAR/0 interaction* OR Two NEAR/3 cell NEAR/3 types OR simultaneously NEAR/3 seeded OR simultaneously NEAR/3 cultured OR Bone NEAR/0 model* OR (Coupling NEAR/5 (bone OR formation OR resorption OR remodeling OR remodelling)) OR Resorption NEAR/2 model OR Mixed NEAR/3 culture OR

Synchronous NEAR/3 cult* OR Simultaneous* NEAR/3 cult* OR binary NEAR/0 cult* OR dual NEAR/0 culture OR bi-cult* OR colocalization OR co-localization OR colocalisation OR co-localisation OR heterocult* OR heterotypic NEAR/3 cult* OR organoid OR organotypic NEAR/3 cult* OR Trans-well OR Transwell OR "Permeable barrier" OR "Well insert" OR "Well inserts" OR "Well-insert" OR "Well-inserts")